

Influence of Technology Differentiation Strategy on Organizational Performance of Insurance Companies in Nakuru East and West Sub-Counties, Kenya

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Abstract: Technology differentiation strategies are the most crucial components for maintaining and improving organizations' performance in a competitive business environment. There has been increased competition and an expanded level of regulations which have intensified the pressure on the insurance business in Kenya. Insurance companies are hence struggling to cope with increased market share competition as well as market dynamics thus difficult to maintain effective organizational performance. This necessitated the examining of the influence of technology differentiation strategy on organizational performance of insurance companies in Nakuru East and West Sub-counties. The study was anchored on Porter's Generic Strategies Theory. It adopted a census technique to include all the branch managers and office administrators of insurance companies. Questionnaires were used in data collection and were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical techniques with aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences. The descriptive and inferential findings showed that technology differentiation strategy influences organizational performance. The study concluded that technology differentiation strategy enables insurance companies to distinguish their services from competitors. The ability to apply differentiated technology makes insurance companies appeal more to the customers in providing policies and associated services. This increases product attractiveness and leads to increased revenue and profitability. The study recommends the integration of technology differentiation strategy into strategic management plans to promote efficiency, product innovativeness, and uniqueness required in the changing business environment.

Keywords: Technology Differentiation Strategy, Organizational Performance, Insurance Companies

1. Introduction

Differentiation strategies, particularly the technology differentiation strategy are important in the operations of insurance companies (Torkestani, Mazloomi, & Haghghat, 2014). Technology differentiation strategy is vital in innovations as well as inventing products and processes to become market leaders from a strategic point of view. As such, innovated products and processes are outcomes of technology differentiation strategies. Bayraktar, Hancerliogullari, Cetinguc, and Calisir (2017) opined that Product-level differentiation is the most meaningful strategy for achieving long-term organizational goals among insurance companies. It offers the desired quality as well as uniqueness that enables an organization to compete favorably against its industry counterparts. The need for incorporating technology use in strategy-based decision-making among insurance companies cannot be overemphasized (Jones & Linderman, 2014). The markets for insurance markets are changing at an accelerating rate, and these changes lead to more demand for unique products by the insurance company customers. Adjustments are not only needed in the products alone but also in the process and ways in which they are availed to the intended clients (Bayraktar et al., 2017). Therefore, the bond between technology use and company strategy is so strong that the establishment and implementation of technology differentiation strategy have become a significant ingredient for effective performance.

Technology differentiation strategy is suitably positioned in promoting effective performance in highly competitive markets (Kaliappen & Hilman, 2017). It promotes favorable competitive positions for differentiating the products and associated processes from other organizations. In Kenya, the insurance companies have been resilient even though they

are operating in a developing economy (Mungai, 2015). Nevertheless, insurance companies have challenges in developing and implementing effective technology differentiation strategies. They are finding it difficult to cope with changing business environment, increased customer demand on product aspects, and regulations. Lack of effective technology differentiation strategies has deterred insurance companies from suiting the evolving needs due to the inability to move with the speed upon which customer preferences change. Bukirwa and Kisingu (2017) noted that organizational performance is determined by products that possess attractive qualities to the customers. Therefore, the lack of effective technology differentiation strategies is attributable to ineffective organizational performance among insurance companies.

Insurance companies in Kenya have experienced inadequate performance as insurance sector profitability decreased by 4.3% which declined from Kshs.15.01 billion to 14.3 billion for the year 2018 according to Insurance Regulatory Report for the year 2018. The insurance industry had been forecasted to increase premiums by 0.4 billion from 2014 to 2018. However, this expectation was not met due to slow growth and ineffective organizational performance. Technology differentiation strategy is at the focal point of effective performance in terms of efficiency, use of technology, customer focus, and product quality (Mutembei & Njuguna, 2019). However, the adoption of differentiation strategies by insurance companies is still slow in Kenya. There is insufficient research information on technology differentiation strategy and insurance sector performance. Muia (2017) took a generalist approach in predicting insurance performance from a competitive advantage. Further, the market penetration strategies applied by Mutegi 2018 did not address the issues of concern about differentiation strategies. The current study examined the influence of technology differentiation strategy on the organizational performance of insurance companies.

2. Objective of the Study

The objective of the study was to examine the influence of technology differentiation strategy on the organizational performance of insurance companies in Nakuru East and West Sub-Counties.

3. Review of Literature

Technology differentiation strategy enhances planning and identification of changes in products' needs in time and deploys technology redesigning products and processes to meet the customers' changing needs (Felício & Rodrigues, 2015). Therefore, technology differentiation strategy streamlines and integrates the culture, infrastructure, and efficiency, and business relationships in insurance companies. The use of technology as a competitive advantage technology facilitates the communication between customers and organizations hence promoting quick and clear interactions (Bayraktar et al., 2017). The public image of insurance companies improves with technology utilization in employee-customer interactions. The websites of insurance companies are designed per the technology differentiation strategy and provide platforms for feedback and answers to the questions by customers concerning products (Kaliappen & Hilman, 2017). Furthermore, technology differentiation is crucial in research and development by insurance companies. Insurance companies research and obtain new opportunities that enhance survival and help them operate ahead of competitors (Felício & Rodrigues, 2015).

According to Yanney (2014), technology is an important part of a business strategy with long-term implications on organizational performance. Therefore, the deployment of technology resources contributes significantly to insurance companies' market share and revenue growth. Abishua (2010) opined that financial sector institutions employ strategies of information technology and diversified product offering in response to competitive pressures. The power of technology has improved organizations' marketing capability in varied sectors of the economy (Su, Peng, Shen, & Xiao, 2013). The technological capabilities and marketing role are almost inseparable in firms intending to respond successfully to a turbulent business environment.

Advancements in technology have contributed to high-voltage transformations in insurance sector strategies leading to the emergence and increased use of a technology differentiation strategy (Hua & Yongquan, 2013). Differentiation strategy regarding technology promotes more involvement of the insurance customers, where their views and concerns are converted into insights used in evaluations and risk assessment (Felício & Rodrigues, 2015). It is usually the differentiator that determines organizational performance. This makes it critically necessary for the insurances to keep pace with technological changes to maintain their competitiveness in the market. Aggarwal, Kapoor, and Gupta (2013) opined that technology differentiation is the key enable of revenue growth among insurance companies.

Empirical studies have been undertaken to determine the effect of differentiation strategies on performance. Kogo and Kimencu (2018) examined the association between organizational capabilities and insurance companies' performance. The study revealed that insurance companies apply marketing capabilities in product development to promote performance. The new attributes of the products are meant to meet the needs of the customers and also the attraction of new

policyholders. The research was cognizant of the shocks posed by the competition in the market. Therefore, insurance companies applied capabilities to strengthen their market positions and survival. The technological capability was prioritized; thus, the personnel was equipped with informational technology to serve the customers in the best way possible. The use of new technologies was also employed to achieve a competitive advantage and good organizational performance.

Mutembei and Njuguna (2019) examined the competitive strategies and market penetration by insurance companies in Kenya. Both the inferential and descriptive research findings showed that market share, as an indicator of performance, is determined by insurance companies' competitive strategies. They affected insurance penetration as well as uptake of insurance policy products. The insurance companies' size also determines their ability to penetrate areas that were unserved previously and increased market share and profits in the process. Further, the strategy of cost leadership played a critical role in enhancing insurance penetration. This strategy was informed by the need for price attractiveness to potential customers. Therefore, based on the findings, insurance companies had to be more efficient in the costs incurred in creating and providing products.

Muia (2017) sought to establish whether insurance companies' performance was affected by competitive advantages. The study's findings revealed that insurance companies emphasized cost leadership, thus worked towards economizing the material costs, and offered a wide range of insurance policy products. They also employed the product differentiation aspect of competitive strategies in offering a wide variety of products to the customers. In the inferential analysis, it was found that the differentiation strategy had a significant and strong association with insurance companies' performance. The study results further showed that insurance companies were more focused on the pricing of products and promotional activities. They offered products at prices lower than the industry counterparts to stabilize the market share. They indicated that customers are more sensitive to prices and thus worked hard to be efficient and maintain the right quality. Additionally, the findings indicated that insurance companies embraced the use of technology through service automation. Finally, the findings showed that the strategy of leadership was important in enhancing the performance of insurance companies.

The past empirical studies reveal significant research gaps. For instance, there were gaps in the study by Muia (2017) regarding the link between differentiation strategies and insurance companies' performance. The study employed all the competitive strategies' components, but more specifically, the differentiation strategy was not explained adequately. The current study has analyzed the differentiation strategies, particularly technology differentiation regarding its influence on insurance companies' organizational performance. The researcher also identified a gap by Kogo and Kimencu (2018), who established the association between insurance companies' organizational capabilities and performance. Technology differentiation strategy was hence derived from the technology capabilities. The current study applied technology differentiation strategy, in addressing the gap identified from Mutembei and Njuguna (2019). Their research focused on market penetration strategies and not technology differentiation strategies for organizational performance.

4. Research Methodology

The study applied a descriptive research design. A descriptive research design takes a systematic and accurate approach to describe a population or sample (Smith, 2019). Therefore, it involves observing and describing the items under the study without influencing them. A descriptive research design helped the researcher to obtain adequate and more detailed information. It also facilitated a description of differentiation strategies and organizational performance of insurance companies. The study targeted 30 registered insurance companies which are based in Nakuru East and West Sub-Counties, Kenya. It is comprised of branch managers and administrators. The accessible population has been specifically chosen because they directly deal with the clients and, hence, they were in a position to give reliable information for the study. The Census technique was employed where all insurance branch managers and administrators were involved in the study. Questionnaires were used in data collection due to their suitability for descriptive studies and avoidance of respondent biases. The questionnaires took the form of Likert statements to enhance the respondent's convenience. The study applied both descriptive and inferential methods in analyzing data. In inferential analysis, Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient and Multivariate Linear Regression Analysis methods were adopted. The Statistical Package aided the undertaking of data analysis for Social Sciences.

5. Results

This section outlines the descriptive and inferential findings that demonstrate the influence of technology differentiation strategy on organizational performance of insurance companies.

5.1: Influence of technology differentiation strategy on organizational performance.

The study sought to determine the influence technology differentiation strategy on organizational performance of insurance companies. Descriptive findings are illustrated on Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive Findings and Discussions for Technology Differentiation Strategy

Technology Differentiation Strategy	N	SA 5	A 4	N 3	D 2	SD 1	Mean	Std. Dev.
The company has the technological capability and efficiency for success in the industry.	48	43.7%	50%	6.3%	-	-	4.37	.606
The company has successfully deployed the acquired technologies to its advantage.	48	41.6%	35.4%	16.7%	6.3%	-	4.13	.914
The company has integrated the technology into the firm processes as required.	48	41.6%	39.6%	16.7%	2.1%	-	4.21	.798
Our company has applied technology in streamlining employee-customer relations.	48	45.8%	31.3%	14.6%	8.3%	-	4.15	.967
Our Company has effectively utilized technological resources in product risk control.	48	41.6%	52.1%	2.1%	2.1%	2.1%	4.29	.798
Our company has a diversified product offering to cope with competition pressures.	48	33.3%	43.7%	18.8%	2.1%	2.1%	4.04	.898

Table 1 shows that the majority of the insurance firms surveyed have the technological capability and efficiency for success in the industry as indicated by the majority (93.7%; mean=4.37; std. dev=.606) of the respondents who agreed. This shows that the firms had recognized the role of technology as a key market differentiator in the industry and had made substantial investments to improve their technological resources. The mean of 4.37 is high above that of the other items in the table suggesting that the firms valued technological capability and efficiency and had strongly emphasized them. Capability and efficiency are important to technology differentiation as they are the key technology-aided performance drivers in an organization with the ability to increase outreach, faster data processing, cost reduction, improved subscription, and product compliance and increases insurance revenues hence enhancing organizational performance. Other findings suggest that the majority of the insurance companies utilize technological resources in product risk control as indicated by the majority (93.7%; mean=4.29; std. dev=.798) of the insurance managers and administrators who agreed with the statement. This indicates that the insurance firms had recognized the potential of technology differentiation strategy as being instrumental in controlling product risks, such as, maintaining adequate levels of returns, which is an indicator of desirable organizational performance in insurance companies. The descriptive findings show that the organizational performance of insurance companies is dependent on the technology differentiation strategy. The suitability and relevance of the unique products established through differentiated technology promote revenue growth and organizational performance. These findings concur with Su et al (2013), whose study on whether technological capability and marketing capability are complementary or supplementary capabilities found that technological capacity and marketing capability have synergistic effects and thus can be a significant differentiator in the market, giving the firm significant competitive advantage.

According to the study findings, the technology differentiation strategy affects organizational performance. Porter's generic strategies theory supports the view that technology differentiation strategy and organizational performance. Porter (2008) explains that in differentiation strategy a firm seeks to be unique in its industry along some dimensions that are widely valued by buyers. It selects one or more attributes that many buyers in an industry perceive as important and uniquely positions it to meet those needs. The firm must endeavor to reduce its costs as much as possible. This could translate to a competitive advantage for the firm not only over its rivals but also over its suppliers and clients as well (Porter, 2008). To develop this strategy, several conditions are required: the firm must have a high market share that

generates high sales volume. In this way the managers can benefit from learning and experience; the firm leaders must ensure the high performance of those factors that permit a reduction in the unit cost of production; technology must be used to ensure that goods are made at the lowest possible cost. Proprietary technology is a key differentiator that offers low costs and high volumes of work. The utilization of technology resources should further enhance product uptake, increase revenue, and contribute to better organizational performance.

5.2: Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis was performed to establish the relationship between technology differentiation strategy and organizational performance of insurance companies. Findings are illustrated on Table 2.

Table 2: Correlation between Technology Differentiation Strategy and Organizational Performance

		Organizational Performance
Technology	Pearson Correlation	.715**
Differentiation Strategy	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	48

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation analysis findings show that technology differentiation strategy was highly correlated to insurance companies’ organizational performance. The correlation coefficient was strong, positive and statistically significant ($r=.715^{**}$; $p=.000$) at 1% significance level. It implies that technology differentiation strategy contributed to increased market share and profitability among the insurance companies. Use of differentiate technology promoted development of unique products that met the insurance customer needs. The differentiation strategy gave the insurance companies a competitive edge against the competitors. It expanded their company capability regarding provision of distinctive services to the customers. The strong correlation coefficient means that an increase in the effectiveness or usefulness of technology differentiation strategy led to more large increase in organizational performance. As such, the technology differentiation strategy influenced organizational performance at a great extent. This finding agrees with Pulungan et al (2018) who found that firm strategy affects technology orientation positively and significantly and this in turn affected company performance positively and significantly.

5.3: Regression Analysis

Regression analysis was performed to indicate the relationship through the prediction of organizational performance from changes in technology differentiation strategy. The regression analysis incorporates the regression model, ANOVA and the coefficients as shown on Tables 3, 4 and 5.

Table 3: Regression Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.715 ^a	.512	.501	.30659

a. Predictors: (Constant), Technology Differentiation Strategy.

Table 3 shows that the relationship between differentiation strategies and organizational performance was very strong, positive and statistically significant ($R=.715$). Therefore, an increase in differentiation strategies contributes to greater increase in organizational performance. The coefficient of determination ($R^2= .512$) showed that 51.2% of variations in organizational performance were explained by changes in technology differentiation strategy.

Table 4: Analysis of Variance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4.537	1	4.537	48.204	.000 ^b
	Residual	4.330	46	.094		
	Total	8.867	47			

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Technological Differentiation Strategy.

Analysis of Variance was undertaken to determine the fitness of the regression model to the data. It was also meant to test overall significance of the model thus established the effect of technology differentiation strategy on organizational performance of insurance companies. The F-value 48.204 was significant at 95% confidence level. Therefore, the relationship between the technology differentiation strategy and organizational performance was significant as the regression model was fit for the data.

Table 5: Regression Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.980	.363		5.451	.000
Technological Differentiation strategy	.596	.086	.715	6.943	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Performance

Table 5 illustrates the regression coefficients consisting of beta coefficients, standard errors, t-values and value of significance/p-values. These values were interpreted using regression model; $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \epsilon$; $Y = 1.980 + .596X_1$

The beta coefficients and significance of the t-values were applied in ascertaining the influence of differentiation strategies on insurance companies' organizational performance. The beta coefficients indicate the units in which the dependent variable changes when one unit changes the independent variable. The t-value is the beta coefficient ratio to the standard errors, which are estimates of standard deviation across the variables. Therefore, the t-values measure the precision of regression coefficients. The regression findings in Table 5 indicate that one unit change in technology differentiation strategy contributed to 0.596 unit change in organizational performance. The t-value for the technology differentiation strategy was 6.943 with sig. value= 0.000 and was significant at 95% confidence level. It implied that technology differentiation strategy influenced the organizational performance of insurance companies in Nakuru East and West Sub-Counties. These findings agree with Atikiya et al. (2015), who found that competitive strategies, especially differentiation strategies, significantly explained firm performance variation. The findings are also in support of other similar studies on differentiation as a competitive strategy, such as Kaliappen (2014), who elaborated differentiation strategy as one of the suitable strategies in competitive strategy for a business to improve their performance.

6. Conclusion

The study concludes that technology differentiation strategy enables insurance companies to distinguish their services from competitors. The ability to apply differentiated technology makes insurance companies appeal more to the customers in providing policies and associated services. This increases product attractiveness and leads to increased revenue and profitability. The study findings indicated that customers are interested in unique services. Their needs keep on changing, thus requiring the insurance companies to embrace technology and dynamism in innovation. Changes and flexibility in developing products that fit the current client preferences require a technology differentiation strategy. Therefore, the market share of insurance companies is determined by the effectiveness of their technology differentiation strategies. Moreover, the capability of the insurance company informed the adoption of a technology differentiation strategy. Its integration indicates the importance of the technology differentiation strategy in promoting revenue growth and organizational performance into the company existing structures and systems. As such, findings showed that different technologies for developing products contributed to organizational performance based on their compatibility and integration into the insurance company.

7. Recommendation

Based on the conclusion on the study findings, insurance companies are recommended to integrate technology differentiation strategy into strategic management plans to promote efficiency, product innovativeness, and uniqueness required in the changing business environment.

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